

A Study of Benign Soft Tissue Tumors in a Tertiary Teaching Hospital: Clinico-Radiological Evaluation

Sayeka Khatun¹, Deb Kumar Biswas², Sharif Anwar Ahmed³

¹Second Year Postgraduate Trainee, Department of Radiology, Murshidabad Medical College and Hospital, Berhampore, West Bengal, India.

²Senior Resident, Department of Radiology, Murshidabad Medical College and Hospital, Berhampore, West Bengal, India.

³Assistant Professor, Department of Radiology, Murshidabad Medical College and Hospital, Berhampore, West Bengal, India.

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Corresponding Author: Dr. Sharif Anwar Ahmed

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Abstract:

Background: Benign soft tissue swellings (BSTS) are a common clinical presentation in tertiary care settings. Accurate diagnosis and management rely heavily on a combination of clinical assessment and radiological imaging. This study aims to evaluate the clinico-radiological approach to diagnosing BSTS in a tertiary teaching hospital.

Methods: A prospective study was conducted on patients presenting with soft tissue swellings at a tertiary teaching hospital over nine months. Clinical examination and history-taking were followed by radiological evaluations, including ultrasound (USG), magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) and computed tomography (CT) and histopathology when necessary. Data on patient demographics, clinical features, radiological and histopathological findings and final diagnoses were collected and analyzed.

Results: A total of 100 patients were included in the study. USG was the first-line imaging modality used in all cases, providing definitive diagnoses for 98% of benign, and 2% malignant lesions. MRI was employed in 3% of cases with equivocal or suspicious lesions, offering superior detail for deep-seated and vascular swellings. HPE was utilized in 10% of cases to assess atypical cases to confirm the findings obtained from USG. The most common benign lesions identified were lipomas, epidermal inclusion cysts and ganglion cysts. Radiological findings were consistent with clinical diagnoses in 90% of the cases.

Conclusion: The integration of clinical and radiological evaluations is crucial for the accurate diagnosis and management of benign soft tissue swellings. USG remains the primary imaging tool, with MRI and histopathology and detailed insights when necessary. Early and precise diagnosis through a clinico-radiological approach ensures optimal patient care and management outcomes.

Keywords: Benign Soft Tissue Swellings, Clinico-radiological Evaluation, Ultrasound, MRI, CT Scan, Tertiary Teaching Hospital.

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Introduction

Soft tissue tumors are diverse growths arising from various connective tissues, encompassing a range of benign entities with varying morphologies and clinical behaviors. Accurately diagnosing these tumors remains challenging due to their nuanced radiological presentations and histopathological heterogeneity. Radiological imaging, serving as a cornerstone in diagnosis, provides vital insights into tumor characteristics such as size, location, and tissue composition. However, integrating radiological findings with clinical and pathological data is essential for comprehensive evaluation.

In our study, conducted within the domain of a tertiary teaching hospital, we focused on the clinico-radiological evaluation of benign soft tissue tumors.

We examined 100 patients with suspected soft tissue tumors, of which 87 were confirmed through ultrasound (USG), showcasing the efficacy of this imaging modality in diagnosis. For the remaining 13 patients, we utilized MRI scans and pathological analysis to confirm the diagnosis and further elucidate tumor characteristics. Moreover, we have found 98% soft tissue lesions are benign and the remaining 2% cases are malignant.

By correlating radiological findings from USG and MRI with clinical manifestations and pathological analysis, we aimed to elucidate the intricate relationship between these domains. Our research endeavor sought to uncover crucial associations, potential discrepancies, and significant contributing

factors underlying the convergence of radiology and pathology in the context of soft tissue tumor evaluation. Through a meticulous examination of these correlations, we endeavored to enhance diagnostic accuracy, refine therapeutic strategies, and optimize patient care in the realm of benign soft tissue tumors.

This paper delineates our study methodology, which involved a combination of imaging modalities and pathological analysis, presents the findings of our clinico-radiological evaluation, discusses their implications for clinical practice, and proposes avenues for future research.

Baloji A et al., [1] studied the combined use of conventional ultrasonography, color Doppler, and elastography strain ratios offers a highly effective, non-invasive diagnostic tool for superficial soft tissue lesions, potentially reducing the need for unnecessary biopsies. The benefits of this integrated ultrasound approach are clear and well-established. The study done by Catalano O. et al., [2] finds soft-tissue palpable lesions are common in clinical practice, and a systematic clinical and sonographic approach is essential for their evaluation. Multiparametric ultrasound, including color-power Doppler, spectral Doppler, and elastography, is highly effective due to its high spatial resolution in superficial tissues. While many benign lesions can be confidently diagnosed with ultrasound, overlapping features may necessitate further imaging like MRI, fine-needle aspiration (FNA), biopsy, or surgical excision, especially when malignancy is suspected. Aparisi Gómez MP et al., [3] study shows that the majority of soft tissue masses are benign, with conditions like superficial lipomas and ganglia being the most common and easily identified using USG. USG is an ideal and cost-effective triaging tool for superficial soft tissue masses, offering high-resolution imaging and allowing real-time interaction with patients. However, when lesions appear atypical, are deep or large, or when malignancy is suspected, further evaluation with MRI and biopsy is necessary. Management of suspicious tumors should involve a multidisciplinary team at a specialized tumor center.

This paper is organized as follows: Following this introductory section, we delve into the existing literature concerning benign soft tissue tumors, highlighting the challenges in diagnosis and the significance of radiological findings in Section II. Subsequently, in Section III, the methodology section provides a detailed exposition of the study design, patient population, imaging modalities used, pathological analysis methods, and the approach employed to correlate radiological findings. In Section IV, the results section illuminates the findings of the study, followed by a comprehensive discussion, emphasizing the implications for clinical practice in Section V. Finally, the conclusion

synthesizes the key findings, and their significance in Section VI

Aims and Objectives

- Develop a radiological method for evaluating soft tissue swellings.
- Characterize different types of soft tissue swellings based on imaging features.
- Assess soft tissue swellings using various imaging techniques to provide accurate diagnoses and assist clinicians in treatment planning.

Materials & Methods

The study was conducted for 9 months from August 2023 to April 2024 in the Department of Radiodiagnosis, Murshidabad Medical College and Hospital, in collaboration with the Department of Surgery and other referral departments of Murshidabad Medical College, Berhampore, Murshidabad. A minimum number of 100 cases were taken up.

The total number of patients included in our study was 100 satisfying our inclusion criteria. They were primarily evaluated by HRUSG, out of 100 cases, 87 were diagnosed on USG and the rest equivocal cases were secondarily evaluated with MRI, histopathology and CT, out of which three were diagnosed with MRI with contrast, and ten were diagnosed with histopathology. It is worth emphasizing that a minimum number of 100 cases were taken up in our study; however, it may be extended depending on the availability of cases and the assigned study period, but we do not expect any deviation from our findings at the statistical level.

Study Design

The present study adopts a prospective analysis of benign soft tissue tumors diagnosed within the Murshidabad Medical College and Hospital, WB, over a period of nine months.

The inclusion criteria and exclusion criteria mentioned before were used to ensure the homogeneity and relevance of the different groups under investigation.

Inclusion Criteria

- Patients with STS of 1–70 years age groups were included in the study.

Exclusion Criteria

The following criteria were excluded from the study:

- Patients who had serious medical problems or were in a lot of pain.
- Pregnant or breastfeeding women, because it's not safe to do a CT scan on them.
- People who were scared of confined spaces (claustrophobia) or had metal inside their bodies, like pacemakers, because they couldn't

have an MRI scan.

- Patients who didn't want to be in the study or didn't give permission.

Equipment

- GE Logiq P9 USG machine with high-resolution linear array probe (3-12 MHz) and hockey stick probe (8-12 MHz).
- OPTIMA MR450w 1.5 Tesla MRI machine with various imaging techniques, including T1-weighted and T2-weighted sequences.

Imaging Modalities and Parameters

A multifaceted approach to radiological imaging was adopted, incorporating MRI, CT, and ultrasound as primary modalities. MRI sequences included T1-weighted, T2-weighted, and contrast-enhanced sequences, focusing on anatomical sites and the nature of swelling. All imaging was performed by experienced radiologists.

Results

Table I: Confirmation of different soft tissue lesions by correlating the USG and other different modalities. The total number of patients was taken to be 100 over the course of nine months.

FT tissue Lesions	Number of Patients	Confirmed by USG	Confirmed by other Modalities (HPE/CT/MRI)
Lipoma	26	22	4 (HPE)
Epidermal inclusion cysts	22	22	0
Ganglion Cysts	18	15	3 (HPE)
Sebaceous Cysts	5	5	0
Dermoid cysts	6	5	1 (HPE)
Peripheral Nerve sheath Tumours	4	2	2 (HPE)
Keloid	1	1	0
Foreign Body	3	3	0
Giant Cell Tumours	3	0	3 (MRI)
Vascular Malformation	5	5	0
Hemangioma	1	1	0
Morel-Lavall'ee lesion	1	1	0
Lymph Node	3	3	0
Abscess	2	2	0

Table II: Gender-wise distributions of soft-tissue lesions

Soft tissue Lesions	Male	Female	Male [%]	Female [%]
Lipoma	16	10	16 %	10 %
Epidermal inclusion cysts	14	8	14 %	8 %
Ganglion Cysts	10	8	10 %	8 %
Dermoid Cysts	4	2	4 %	2 %
Sebaceous cysts	4	1	4 %	1 %
Peripheral Nerve sheath Tumours	3	1	3 %	1 %
Keloid	1	0	1 %	0 %
Foreign Body	2	1	2 %	1 %
Giant Cell Tumours	2	1	2 %	1 %
Vascular Malformation	3	2	3 %	2 %
Hemangioma	1	0	1 %	0 %
Morel-Lavall'ee lesion	1	0	1 %	0 %
Lymph Node	2	1	2 %	1 %
Abscess	2	0	2 %	0 %

Table III: Location-wise distributions of soft-tissue lesions

Soft Tissue Lesions	Upper Extremities [%]	Lower Extremities [%]	Trunk [%]	Head & Neck [%]
Lipoma	7 [7 %]	4 [4 %]	13 [13 %]	2 [2 %]
Epidermal inclusion cysts	5 [5 %]	3 [3 %]	3 [3 %]	11 [11 %]
Ganglion Cysts	12 [12 %]	6 [6 %]	0 [0 %]	0 [0 %]
Dermoid Cysts	1 [1 %]	0 [0 %]	2 [2 %]	3 [3 %]
Sebaceous cysts	1 [1 %]	0 [0 %]	1 [1 %]	3 [3 %]
Peripheral Nerve sheath Tumours	3 [3 %]	0 [0 %]	0 [0 %]	1 [1 %]
Keloid	0 [0 %]	0 [0 %]	1 [1 %]	0 [0 %]

Foreign Body	2 [2 %]	1 [1 %]	0 [0 %]	0 [0 %]
Giant Cell Tumours	3 [3 %]	0 [0 %]	0 [0 %]	0 [0 %]
Vascular Malformation	2 [2 %]	1 [1 %]	0 [0 %]	2 [2 %]
Hemangioma	0 [0 %]	0 [0 %]	0 [0 %]	1 [1 %]
Morel-Lavall'ee lesion	0 [0 %]	1 [1 %]	0 [0 %]	0 [0 %]
Lymph Node	0 [0 %]	0 [0 %]	0 [0 %]	3 [3 %]
Abscess	1 [1 %]	1 [1 %]	0 [0 %]	0 [0 %]

Figure 1: Left Panel: sonographically the lesion appears as a well-defined, hypoechoic mass in the subcutaneous layer, showing posterior acoustic enhancement and lacking vascularity. Right Panel: HPE - the lesion is lined with stratified squamous epithelium and doesn't contain skin appendages. These features collectively confirm the diagnosis of an epidermal inclusion cyst.

Figure 2: HRUSG depicts a well-defined heterogeneous hypoechoic lesion in the subcutaneous plane adjacent to the radial nerve. The colour doppler image indicates internal vascularity within the lesion. Histological appearance -Spindle cells showing nuclear Palisading

Figure 3: Left Panel: The HRUSG image reveals a Hypoechoic cystic lesion with internal echoes noted between the subcutaneous fat and fascial layer suggesting a Morel Lavelle lesion. Right Panel: HRUSG depicts a well-defined heterogeneous hypoechoic lesion with a dilated tortuous structure and on colour Doppler variable vascularity noted within it suggests vascular malformation

Figure 4: HRUSG reveals a Hypoechoic, homogeneous, solid mass noted over the dorsal aspect of the proximal phalanx encasing the extensor tendon of the ring finger Color Doppler reveals Central as well as peripheral vascularity MRI reveals - T1 weighted sequence -The lesion is hypointense and On a T2 weighted sequence it appear hyperintense and on a contrast-enhanced T1 weighted sequence -it shows heterogeneous enhancement.

Figure 5: Left panel: HRUSG depicts well defined encapsulated lesion with a similar eco-pattern to the fat at the site of swelling with linear echogenic striations within it and without any internal vascularity. Right Panel: The H & E stained section displays a layer of mature fat cells divided by fibrous partitions. We can infer by analysing both the figures that it is lipoma

Figure 6: The HRUSG image reveals an echogenic linear structure causing posterior acoustic shadowing, surrounded by a hypoechoic collection. It can be understood from the figure that it is a foreign body.

Our aim was to classify the tumors based on their origin and nature. Benign tumors were more common than malignant ones in our study. We primarily used high-resolution grayscale ultrasound and Doppler as the initial diagnostic tools for evaluating these superficial soft tissue tumors due to their applicability, availability, and relatively low cost. USG also offers advantages such as good spatial and contrast resolution, as well as real-time imaging capability.

In our study, all 100 patients underwent initial evaluation with USG. Among them, 87 were confirmed by USG, three patients required further evaluation with USG and MRI and the remaining

ten patients were needed additional imaging with USG and histopathology for diagnosis. The most common findings were lipomas, followed by epidermal inclusion cysts, with Morel-Lavallée lesion and keloid being less common.

Here we very briefly describe the figures as shown in the result section. In Fig. 1 we can see that the lesion is a well-defined hypoechoic mass located in the subcutaneous plane. Notably, it exhibits posterior acoustic enhancement, which means that the echoes behind the mass appear brighter due to the fluid-filled nature of the lesion. Additionally, there is no internal vascularity, which further supports the diagnosis of an epidermal inclusion

cyst. Based on Fig. 2, the ul-trasound appearance of the lesion shows that it is well-defined, heterogeneous, hypoechoic, and exhibits mild internal vascularity. Additionally, the lesion is located adjacent to the radial nerve. Histopathological findings reveal a spindle cell pattern with nuclear palisading. Considering these features, we can conclude that it is a case of peripheral nerve sheath tumor. In Fig. 3: Morel-Lavall'ee Lesion: On ultrasound (USG), the lesion appears as a well-defined hypoechoic lesion with internal echoes noted between the subcutaneous fat and fascial layer. The patient has a history of trauma, which is suggestive of a Morel-Lavall'ee lesion. Vascular Malformation: In the same figure, the lesion is described as a hypoechoic heterogeneous mass. Within the mass, there are dilated tortuous structures. Color Doppler shows variable vascularity, indicating a vascular malformation. From Fig. 4: a well-defined hypoechoic homogeneous solid mass is observed over the dorsal aspect of the proximal phalanx. This mass encases the extensor tendon of the ring finger. On both USG and MRI, it shows central and peripheral vascularity, the mass appears hypointense on T1-weighted sequences. Conversely, it appears hyperintense on T2-weighted sequences. During contrast-enhanced T1-weighted sequences, there is heterogeneous enhancement.

Based on these findings, the diagnosis is suggestive of a Giant cell tumor of the tendon sheath. Based on Fig. 5, we can confirm the diagnosis of a lipoma using sonography. The key features include a well-defined, hypoechoic lesion with parallel echogenic striations and absence of internal vascularity. Additionally, histopathological examination supports this diagnosis. Finally, from Fig. 6, the ultrasound reveals a linear echogenic structure with posterior acoustic shadowing. Additionally, there is a surrounding hypoechoic collection, which is indicative of a foreign body.

Brief description about soft tissue lesions

Lipoma

A lipoma is a common, benign tumor composed of mature fat cells, presenting as a soft, painless, and movable lump under the skin, commonly found on the neck, shoulders, back, and extremities. On ultrasonography, lipomas appear well-defined and hyperechoic or isoechoic. MRI reveals them as hyperintense on T1 and T2 images, with a signal drop on fat-suppressed sequences. CT shows them as low-attenuation, well-defined masses. Diag-nosis is primarily clinical, confirmed by imaging, and treatment involves surgical excision if the lipoma is symptomatic, rapidly growing, or cosmetically concerning.

Table IV: Characterization of the swellings based on their sonographic features

Characterisation of Swelling	Sonographic Appearance	Number of Patients	Percentage
Based on ecopattern	Hypoechoic	38	38 %
	Hyperechoic	26	26 %
	Anechoic	17	17 %
	Heteroechoic	19	19 %
Based on nature	Cystic	49	49%
	Solid	30	30%
	Mixed	21	21%
Based on the Anatomical plane of origin	Superficial	84	84 %
	Deep	16	16 %
Based on Mergin of the lesions	Well defined	95	95%
	Poorly defined	2	2%
	Lobulated	3	3%
Based on Vascularity using colour doppler	Avascular	84	84%
	Minimal Vascularity	7	7%
	Profound Vascularity	7	7%
	Peripheral Vascularity	2	2%

Epidermal Inclusion Cysts

An epidermal inclusion cyst (EIC) is a benign cystic lesion that arises from the epidermis. Its radiological features include:

Ultrasound: Well-defined, hypoechoic to anechoic mass with posterior acoustic enhancement. May have internal echoes or debris.

CT Scan: Well-circumscribed, low-attenuation lesion. Sometimes shows a central punctate calcification.

Ganglion Cysts

A ganglion cyst has specific radiological features:

Ultrasound: Well-defined, anechoic or hypoechoic mass, often with posterior acoustic enhancement.

May have internal septations.

MRI: Homogeneously low signal on T1-weighted images and high signal on T2-weighted images. The cyst usually has a well-defined, thin wall and does not enhance with contrast, though the wall itself may enhance slightly.

Sebaceous Cysts

A sebaceous cyst, also known as an epidermoid cyst, has distinct radiological features:

Ultrasound: Well-defined, hypoechoic or anechoic mass with posterior acoustic enhancement. May show internal debris or keratin material.

MRI: Typically shows variable signal intensity, often low to intermediate on T1-weighted images and high on T2-weighted images. The cyst may have a hypointense capsule and usually does not enhance with contrast.

Figure 7: Distribution of percentage of patients depending on age, sex and location of swellings

Dermoid Cysts

A dermoid cyst, a type of benign cystic teratoma, has distinct radiological features:

USG: Complex, cystic mass with mixed echogenicity, often with a solid component and posterior acoustic shadowing due to calcifications or hair.

MRI: Heterogeneous signal intensity, with high signal on T1-weighted images due to fat content and variable signal on T2-weighted images. Fat suppression sequences confirm the presence of fat. May show a complex internal structure and lack significant contrast enhancement.

Peripheral Nerve Sheath Tumors

Peripheral nerve sheath tumors, such as schwannomas and neurofibromas, exhibit distinct radiological features:

USG: Hypoechoic, well-defined mass. May show internal heterogeneity and some vascularity on color Doppler imaging.

MRI: Schwannomas: Typically well-circumscribed, with isointense to hypointense signal on T1-weighted images and hyperintense signal on T2-weighted images. Often show heterogeneous

enhancement after gadolinium administration. Characteristic “target sign” on T2-weighted images (central low signal surrounded by high signal).

Neurofibromas: More likely to be fusiform and infiltrative. Isointense to hypointense on T1, hyperintense on T2-weighted images. Homogeneous or heterogeneous enhancement with gadolinium. “Target sign” can also be present.

Keloid

Keloids, which are over growths of scar tissue, have the following radiological features:

Ultrasound: Hypoechoic or heterogeneous mass with irregular borders. Increased vascularity may be seen on color Doppler imaging.

MRI: Typically hypointense on T1-weighted images and hyperintense on T2-weighted images. Post-contrast images often show enhancement due to the fibrous and vascular nature of the tissue.

Foreign Body: Foreign bodies are objects inadvertently introduced into the body, often causing discomfort or injury. They can be organic (such as wood or thorns) or inorganic (such as metal or glass). Imaging modalities like X-ray or CT scan or USG are used to locate and characterize foreign

bodies, aiding in their removal. Radiopaque objects appear bright on X-ray, while radiolucent objects may require additional imaging techniques. Prompt identification and removal are essential to prevent complications.

Giant Cell Tumors

Giant cell tumor of the tendon sheath (GCTTS), also known as localized nodular tenosyn-ovitis, presents with distinct radiological features:

USG: US is commonly used for the evaluation of GCTTS. It typically shows a hypoechoic or isoechoic mass adjacent to the affected tendon sheath. Doppler ultrasound may reveal hypervascularity within the mass.

MRI: MRI is the preferred modality for evaluating GCTTS due to its superior soft tissue contrast. GCTTS appears as a well-defined mass with low to intermediate signal intensity on T1-weighted images and heterogeneous high signal intensity on T2-weighted images. Post-contrast sequences may show heterogeneous enhancement within the mass.

Vascular Malformation

Vascular malformations encompass a diverse group of congenital vascular abnormalities, each with its own unique radiological features. However, some general characteristics can be outlined:

USG: US is often used as the initial imaging modality for evaluating vascular malformations, especially superficial lesions. It can reveal the vascularity, flow characteristics, and extent of the lesion. High-flow lesions, such as AVMs, demonstrate rapid arterial and venous flow with arterialization of the venous system.

MRI: MRI is the modality of choice for assessing the extent and tissue involvement of vascular malformations. It provides excellent soft tissue contrast and can differentiate between different types of malformations. On MRI, vascular malformations typically appear as areas of abnormal signal intensity with flow voids representing fast-flowing vessels.

Morel-Lavall'ee Lesion

Morel-Lavall'ee lesions (MLL) are closed degloving injuries characterized by the separation of the subcutaneous tissue from the underlying fascia due to trauma. Here are the radiological features associated with Morel-Lavall'ee lesions:

USG: MLLs typically appear as fluid collections between the subcutaneous fat and the deep fascia. On ultrasound, they present as hypoechoic or anechoic fluid collections with variable internal echogenicity depending on the age of the lesion and the presence of debris or hemorrhage. Color Doppler ultrasound may show minimal or absent vascularity

within the lesion.

Abscess

Abscesses appear as hypoechoic, well-defined fluid collections on ultrasound. They often have a distinct border and may show some internal echoes. Color Doppler usually reveals minimal or absent blood flow inside. Ultrasound is valuable for pinpointing their location and aiding in drainage procedures.

Discussion

In this section, we are going to discuss the existing literature which has already studied a similar topic namely benign soft tissue tumours and their radiological evolution and carried out the pathological correlations as well when demanded. The topic is very well covered in the literature and we summarize very briefly a few of them.

In the study done by Hiremath R et al., [4] authors have shown soft-tissue swellings (STSs) are frequently encountered in radiology practice, prompting diagnostic examinations or incidental findings during other assessments. The study aimed to establish an approach for STS evaluation using available modalities (USG, CT, MRI) and analyze imaging characteristics for diagnosis. USG primarily diagnosed 72 out of 100 cases, while MRI was beneficial for equivocal or deeply located lesions, diagnosing 25 out of 28 cases. CT served as an adjunct for calcification and bone involvement detection. USG remains the first-line modality, with MRI aiding in characterization and CT assisting in specific scenarios.

In Deepak M.B. et al [5] study, they consider a study of 250 lesions, 85.2% were identified as benign soft tissue tumours. Male predominance was noted (57.4%), with most benign tumours occurring in the third decade (21%) and often in the head and neck region (38%). About 75% of cases measured less than 5 centimeters. Lipoma was the most common tumour (31.9%), followed by capillary hemangioma (13.1%). Surgical excision showed a high cure rate, but aggressive benign myxoid tumours required thorough removal and close monitoring. Overall, managing these tumours effectively necessitates a coordinated approach involving clinical, radiological, and pathological perspectives.

Jon A. Jacobson [6] in their study, qualitatively described that USG serves as an excellent first-line imaging technique for evaluating superficial soft-tissue masses. As discussed earlier in this article, many diagnoses can be confidently established using US. In most other cases, a combination of US findings and clinical history is sufficient to guide appropriate management. However, follow-up, additional imaging, or a biopsy may be necessary for atypical, nonspecific, or suspicious US findings or when the clinical history is conflicting.

The study of Kinare A. et al [7] shows that the soft tissue masses vary in presentation, and while not all are optimally imaged on USG, its easy availability, real-time capability, and cost-effectiveness make it the preferred first-line modality. Doppler, though exciting, has limitations, particularly for superficial masses. USG's role lies in assessing mass extent, nature, and relation to surrounding structures, aiding in differentiating pseudotumors from true lesions, with Doppler offering supplementary insights in select cases. USG-guided needle biopsy facilitates tissue diagnosis. Benign lesions prevail in daily practice, highlighting the importance of technical proficiency and musculoskeletal anatomy knowledge in musculoskeletal examinations.

Beggs I. et al [8] study highlights the clinical and sonographic characteristics of various nerve tumors, focusing on their distinctive ultrasound features and common anatomical locations whereas Sintzoff Jr SA et., [9] study discusses the differential diagnosis of soft tissue lesions, noting that ultrasound can often confirm a diagnosis, with MRI and CT used when ultrasound is inconclusive.

The study of Chiou HJ et al., [10] assessed high-resolution grayscale and color Doppler ultrasound's utility in distinguishing benign from malignant soft-tissue masses. Examining 818 patients with palpable superficial nodules or masses, each lesion underwent detailed ultrasound evaluation. Confirmation of mass nature was achieved through various diagnostic methods. Significant differences ($p < 0.05$) were observed in tumor margin, shape, and size between benign and malignant tumors. However, echogenicity, composition, and color Doppler features showed no significant differences ($p > 0.05$). Ultrasonography with color Doppler imaging proves effective for characterizing most soft-tissue masses, with tumor size > 5 cm and infiltrated margin strongly suggestive of malignancy. Authors in Hung EH et al [11] study evaluated the ultrasound accuracy in defining specific nature and malignancy of 823 superficial soft tissue masses. Ultrasound showed high accuracy (81.2%) compared to clinical examination (25.6%) and histological correlation (95.5%). Radiologists were "fully confident" in 71.1% of cases, with accuracy improving with experience. Sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value, and negative predictive value for identifying malignant tumors were 93.3%, 97.9%, 45.2%, and 99.9%, respectively. Ultrasound exhibits high accuracy in characterizing and distinguishing benign from malignant superficial soft tissue masses.

Numerous comprehensive studies have explored this area. Interested readers are encouraged to explore the references provided earlier and additional references therein for further details. This study is one more addition to this kind of study and we have found a very important results on benign soft tissue

tumours with its radiological and pathological correlations. In our study we have also found similar kind of results as we have discussed so far. Now we are going to describe our findings in detail. In Table I, we have shown our analysis for soft tissue lesions was investigated using various diagnostic methods. The total number of patients considered was 100 over a six-month period. Here are the key findings: Lipoma among the 26 patients studied, confirmed by USG for 22 patients and were confirmed by other modalities (HPE/CT/MRI) for 4 patients. Epidermal Inclusion Cysts were found in 22 patients and confirmed by USG for all of them. Ganglion Cysts were found in 18 patients, Confirmed by USG in 15 patients and remaining were confirmed by other modalities. Sebaceous cysts were found in 5 and all of them were confirmed by USG. Dermoid Cysts were found in 6 patients among them 5 were confirmed by USG and the remaining one by the histopathological examination. The other soft tissues were also mainly confirmed by the USG and most interestingly the giant cell tumours, all of them were confirmed by the MRI. These findings provide insights into the diagnostic accuracy of different imaging techniques for soft tissue lesions. USG can be used in most cases, therefore, researchers and healthcare professionals can use this information to make informed decisions regarding patient care.

In Table II, we have summarized the gender-wise distribution of soft tissue lesions in paragraph form: In a study involving 100 patients, we have investigated the prevalence of various soft tissue lesions based on gender. Here are the key findings based on different soft tissues: Lipoma: Lipomas, benign tumors composed of fat cells, were identified in 16% of males and 10% of females. These growths are typically harmless but can cause discomfort due to their size or location.

Epidermal Inclusion Cysts: Epidermal inclusion cysts, which result from trapped skin cells, occurred in 14% of males and 8% of females. These cysts often present as painless lumps beneath the skin. Ganglion Cysts: Ganglion cysts, filled with fluid from nearby joints or tendons, were observed in 10% of males and 8% of females. They commonly appear on wrists and hands. Sebaceous Cysts: Sebaceous cysts, arising from blocked sebaceous glands, were found in 4% of males and 2% of females. These cysts contain a thick, oily substance. Dermoid Cysts: Dermoid cysts, rare developmental anomalies, were detected in only 1 case (1%) among males and were absent in females. These cysts can contain hair, skin, and other tissues. Peripheral Nerve Sheath Tumors: Peripheral nerve sheath tumors, arising from nerve coverings, affected 3% of males and 1% of females. These tumors can be benign or malignant. Vascular Malformations: Vascular malformations, abnormal blood vessel growth, manifested in 3% of males and 2% of females. These can include hemangiomas and

venous malformations. Hemangioma: Hemangiomas, benign blood vessel tumors, were present in 1% of males but were not observed in females. These growths can occur anywhere in the body. Morel-Lavallee Lesion: Similarly, Morel-Lavallee lesions, caused by trauma and tissue shearing, were seen in 1% of males and were absent in females. These lesions often result from sports injuries or accidents. Lymph Node: Lymph nodes were affected in 2% of males and 1% of females. Enlarged lymph nodes can indicate infection or other underlying conditions. Abscess: Abscesses, localized collections of pus, occurred in 2% of males, while no cases were reported in females. These can result from infections or inflammatory processes. The gender-wise distribution of soft tissue lesions reveals interesting patterns. Lipomas are more prevalent in males, while epidermal inclusion cysts and ganglion cysts show similar occurrence in both genders. Dermoid cysts are rare, and vascular malformations exhibit slight gender differences. Hemangiomas are more common in males, and Morel-Lavallee lesions occur infrequently. Lymph nodes and abscesses also demonstrate gender-specific variations. These insights can guide clinicians in tailoring their diagnostic and treatment approaches based on gender-specific trends.

Table III displays location-wise distributions of soft-tissue lesions. This comprehensive chart categorizes various types of soft tissue lesions based on their location in the human body. The table is divided into five columns representing different body parts: Upper Extremities, Lower Extremities, Trunk, Head & Neck, and Total. The table provides numerical data for each lesion type in different body parts. For example, it indicates the number of lipomas in the upper extremities, lower extremities, trunk, head & neck, and the total count. The percentages represent the proportion of each lesion type within a specific location. For instance, the percentage of lipomas in the upper extremities is 13%. Finally, lipomas and ganglion cysts are prevalent in the upper extremities, dermoid cysts are primarily found in the head and neck region, peripheral nerve sheath tumors are distributed across various body parts.

Table IV describes the characterization of the Swelling based on Sonographic features. We have divided it into four main categories with their subcategories. We listed our description below

First one is echotexture which is categorized based on echotexture, which refers to their appearance in ultrasound imaging. Subcategories and their findings are:

- Hypoechoic: Represents 38 patients (38% of the total). Hypoechoic areas appear darker than surrounding tissues.

- Hyperechoic: Includes 26 patients (26%). Hyperechoic areas appear brighter than surrounding tissues.
- Anechoic: Found in 17 patients (17%). Anechoic areas appear black, indicating fluid-filled regions.
- Heteroechoic: Present in 19 patients (19%). Heteroechoic areas have mixed echogenicity.

The second one is the nature of swelling which is further characterized based on its nature as,

- Cystic: Dominant in 49 patients (49%). Cystic areas are fluid-filled and echo-free.
- Solid: Observed in 30 patients (30%). Solid areas have uniform echogenicity.
- Mixed: Found in 21 patients (21%). Mixed areas combine solid and cystic components.

The third one is the anatomical Plane of origin where swellings are categorized based on their anatomical location:

- Superficial: Represents 84% of cases. Superficial swellings occur near the skin surface.
- Deep: Accounts for 16% of cases. Deep swellings are located deeper within tissues.

Finally, the remaining two are the margin of the lesions and vascularity using Color doppler where most of the cases fall in the Well-defined and avascular category as shown in the table. In Fig. 7, we have shown the distribution of the number of patients in percentage depending on age, sex and location in histogram format.

Conclusion

For the evaluation of soft tissue swellings, radiological diagnosis plays a major role in management as it involves early detection using affordable and radiation-free methods to prevent delays in diagnosis and ensure timely and accurate treatment. Our study reveals the following outcomes,

- USG is the excellent primary imaging method for evaluating soft tissue swellings. Often it allows for a definite diagnosis. By integrating USG results with patients clinical history, healthcare providers can usually determine the best course of action. It's effective for diagnosing benign, cystic and superficial lesions and help in guided drainage procedures. If the USG results are unclear, or suspicious, further imaging modalities or histopathological examination might be needed.
- MRI is the best imaging option for ambiguous or potentially dangerous lesions. It's especially valuable for assessing malignant, vascular and deep-seated lesions. Computer tomography scans serve as a supplementary tool in detecting calcification and mineralisation.

- We have described our investigations on a different kind of soft tissue lesions by displaying a few figures (Figs. (1 – 6)) obtained from different modalities. We have studied the confirmation of soft lesions by different modalities, gender wise, location wise and depending on the characterisation of swellings in Table I, II, III and IV, respectively. We have mentioned in detail in the text that some of the lesions are more prominent in males over females and also prefer particular locations on human body. It is worth mentioning that from our study we have found that 98% cases are benign and 2% cases are malignant.

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References

1. Baloji A, Chandra R, Bagri N, Misra R, Rajni K, Prabhu SS. Diagnostic accuracy of an integrated approach using conventional ultrasonography, and Doppler and strain elastography in the evaluation of superficial soft tissue lesions. *Pol J Radiol*. 2020 Jun 11;85:e293-e300. doi: 10.5114/pjr.2020.96961. PMID: 326850 64; PMCID: PMC7361366.
2. Catalano O, Varelli C, Sbordone C, Corvino A, De Rosa D, Vallone G, Wortsman X. A bump: what to do next? Ultrasound imaging of superficial soft-tissue palpable lesions. *J Ultrasound*. 2020 Sep;23(3):287-300. doi: 10.1007/s40477-019-00415-z. Epub 2019 Nov 30. PMID: 31786796; PMCID: PMC7441113.
3. Aparisi Gómez MP, Errani C, Lalam R, Vasilevska Nikodinovska V, Fanti S, Tagliafico AS, Sconfienza LM, Bazzocchi A. The Role of Ultrasound in the Diagnosis of Soft Tissue Tumors. *Semin Musculoskelet Radiol*. 2020 Apr;24(2):135-155. doi: 10.1055/s-0039-3402060. Epub 2020 May 21. PMID: 3243 8440.
4. Hiremath R, Gowda G, Reddy HT, Ibrahim J, Shah RS, Chodiboina H. Superficial Soft Tissue Swellings: Accuracy of Ultrasonography in Diagnosis with Pathological Correlation. *Journal of Clinical & Diagnostic Research* 2018; 12(1).
5. Deepak MB, Suchitha S, Manjunath GV, IBharadwaj I. Clinico-pathological study of benign soft tissue tumors: a study from tertiary teaching hospital. *Tropical Journal of Pathology and Microbiology* 20162(3):134-41.
6. Jon A. Jacobson, William D. Middleton , Sandra J. Allison, Nirvikar Dahiya, Kenneth S. Lee, Benjamin D. Levine, David R. Lucas, Mark D. Murphey, Levon N. Nazarian, Geoffrey W. Siegel, and Jason M. Wagner, Ultrasonography of Superficial Soft-Tissue Masses: Society of Radiologists in Ultrasound Consensus Conference Statement, *Radiology* 2022 304:1, 18-30
7. Kinare A, Brahmalkar M, Shalini D. Ultrasound of musculoskeletal soft tissue masses. *Indian Journal of Radiology and Imaging* 2007;17(03):201-8.
8. Beggs I. Sonographic appearances of nerve tumors. *Journal of Clinical Ultrasound* 1999; 27(7):363-8.
9. Sintzoff Jr SA, Gillard I, Van Gansbeke D, Gevenois PA, Salmon I, Struyven J. Ultrasound evaluation of soft tissue tumors. *Journal Belge de Radiologie* 1992;75(4):276-80.
10. Chiou HJ, Chou YH, Chiu SY, Wang HK, Chen WM, Chen TH, et al. Differentiation of benign and malignant superficial soft-tissue masses using grayscale and color Doppler ultrasonography. *Journal of the Chinese Medical Association* 2009;72(6):307-15.
11. Hung EH, Griffith JF, Yip SW, Ivory M, Lee JC, Ng AW, Tong CS. Accuracy of ultrasound in the characterization of superficial soft tissue tumors: a prospective study. *Skeletal Radiology* 2020; 49:883-92.